

THE ROLE OF CREATIVE ASPECTS IN THE WORK OF MUSIC TEACHERS

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Abstract. The content of creativity, its aspects, common and differences between creativity and creativity parameters, importance of creativity in pedagogical processes are discussed in the article. The value of creativity parameters in the work of music teachers is discussed.

Keywords. Creativity, creativity, technology, parameter, motivation, aesthetics, emotional, intellectual, communicative, existential.

Attention is paid to the change of the trainee as a result of rapid response to changes in state educational standards, introduction of new methods and forms of work. Understanding the importance of these approaches requires a focus on the creativity of the future teacher in the professional training process. Creativity is formed from Latin "creatio" - "to create", "creative" - "creator", "creative", which is interpreted as the emergence of individual creative abilities. The concept of "creativity" was first used in the history of mankind in 1922 by D. Simpson. The term refers to a person's ability to abandon stereotypical thinking. Later, theoretical and practical research on creativity was carried out by J. Guilford who associated the term "creativity" with a special type of thinking - divergent thinking (from Latin Divergere - "division") [2,444]. Creativity is often associated with the phenomenon of creating something new that has individual or societal significance. Scientific interest in the study of creativity can be observed in various fields - psychology, pedagogy, sociology, philosophy, economics, engineering and other disciplines. Creativity, innovation, intelligence - these are

the intellectual needs of modern society, on the solution of which depend the development prospects and efficiency of all socio-cultural and economic processes. In innovative education, creativity, self-development and creative thinking are above all important. As in all pedagogical fields, the work of today's music teacher is a complex process. It requires the teacher to always be in search of a creative style, to be unconventional, to be able to use new pedagogical and modern technologies. The creative personality is increasingly in demand by society, and its development is known to be the subject of extensive psychological research all over the world. Modern creative psychology is multidimensional and presents many different theories, concepts, theoretical and empirical knowledge. Despite a number of important discoveries, the problem of creativity, especially the phenomenon of creativity, is still an understudied phenomenon. Thus, the search for ways to study creativity as a special mental reality, a complex psychological phenomenon, is an urgent issue of our time. The meaning field of the concept "creativity" is wider than the concept "creative potential", "creative orientation", because the phenomenon of creativity has potential and active forms. A creative person is a person, who realises his or her creative abilities in innovative achievements. Creativity is an integral part of creativity. The difference between the concepts of creativity and creative orientation is that the former is related to intellectual development, while the latter is based on a type of activity that promotes creative thinking.

- Creativity is performance-oriented, creativity is the motivational side of creativity;
- Creativity is a process characterised by the ability to manifest itself in any type of activity, and creativity is a permanent property of the individual;
- Creativity is a constructive activity that creates innovation, creativity is the highest level of intellectual thinking activity;
- Creativity - activity aimed at obtaining new results, creativity - readiness to create new products of social significance [6,5].

Thus, the functional foundations of the concepts of "creative orientation", "creativity" and "creativity" are as follows:

1) Structurally - directionality, creativity will be connected with the subject of activity, creativity - with the decision taken by thought.

2) Activity - creative orientation, if it comes from creativity itself, creativity comes from thinking process.

It should be noted that the future teacher's readiness for creative activity is connected with the presence of self-consciousness as a creative person, creative activity, independence, knowledge, abilities, skills, knowledge, experience of work process organization. For example, V.A. Slasten considers creative training as "a decisive sign of future teacher's professionalism" [7, 224]. Based on the analysis of the literature it can be understood that the psychological structure of creativity includes a system of creative parameters and is a unique combination of motivational, intellectual, aesthetic, existential, communicative parameters as well as competence parameters. The components of creativity determine the style of creative behaviour and characterise productivity, novelty, unique way of working, inclination of a person to creative changes in various spheres of life, readiness. A music teacher should be creative and innovative in his or her search for the most appropriate ways of teaching and developing students' creative abilities. The creativity of the teacher covers different aspects of his activity: communication with the class, performing various creative exercises, work on organizing children's collectives, taking into account age and individual characteristics, optimal solution of problems of developing strategies and tactics of pedagogical activity, etc. . It is through creativity that the child not only assimilates events of reality and behaviour in artistic form, but also transforms itself as a personality with a definite social, moral and aesthetic orientation. The sequence of stages in the teacher's creative process can be summarised as follows:

- emergence of a pedagogical concept aimed at solving a pedagogical problem - concepts about reality, methods, technologies, factors of the learning

process in general, which he/she considers a problem in his/her field; - development of thought - with the emergence of concepts, thought develops in the analysis of pedagogical processes through the necessary, unnecessary, necessary, insignificant, etc.; - analysis, evaluation of the creative result and directing pedagogical means to it - after the creative approach, along with the analysis of its results, a certain degree of effectiveness is evaluated and, accordingly, new ideas or existing means are directed to the next creative process.

The future music teacher, being acquainted with different subjects, types of lessons, forms and methods of teaching in higher education, will try to apply the acquired knowledge and skills in the future pedagogical activity, creatively approach lessons, make conclusions. for him/her. At the same time it is necessary to help the teacher to develop the skills of creative approach in each process, effectively and simultaneously increase the creativity of the most necessary skills during the student's period. In general secondary education music lessons, the teacher plays a leading role in shaping the students' music competences, and creativity plays an important role in this.

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